

THE ROLE OF DIFFERENTIAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT EXERCISE SKILLS

Khaidarov B.Y.

Senior teacher, The department of Sports Activities, Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13882660>

Abstract. *This article examines the importance of differential education in forming the skills of independent performance of exercises in students. The main principles and methods of differentiated education are analyzed in detail, as well as how this approach develops the ability to perform exercises according to the individual needs of students. The study shows the possibility of providing students with customized exercises, improving their independent work and increasing their motivation through differentiated education. The article also discusses the practical recommendations and results of using an individual approach in the educational process, which is important for improving the quality of education and improving students' self-management skills.*

Keywords: *independent performance, differential education, individual characteristics, independent education, elementary school students, educational process.*

The role of differential education is of great importance in the formation of students' skills of independent performance of exercises. Differentiated learning methods help ensure that students complete exercises in a timely and effective manner by taking into account the individual characteristics of students. This approach offers exercises tailored to each student's unique needs and abilities, which enhances the development of independent work skills. Also, with the help of differentiated education, students are given tasks adapted to their abilities, and an opportunity is created for them to fully realize their potential.

Also, priority is given to differential education and completion of individual assignments as an effective way of forming students' skills for independent education.

Differentiated education is a form of organizing the educational process in which the teacher works with students (homogeneous class) who are united in one group with certain common characteristics. The differential education system provides a special learning process for different groups of students. Mainly, the following features are paid attention to in Differential education:

- according to the composition of age characteristics;
- according to the division into boys and girls;
- by areas of interest;
- according to the level of mental development;
- depending on the level of health.

Scientists who studied the theory of differential education, such as E.A. Yamburg, V.D. Shadrikov, believe that the personal characteristics of students are the basis of differential education, and those characteristics are manifested depending on the child's teaching and learning, work ability, type of thinking.

By applying differential teaching methods, students' knowledge of physical culture improves, the level of mastery of science increases, children's readiness to independently perform comprehensive exercises, motor skills improve, and the number of participants in school sports competitions increases. We present excerpts of differential tasks from a specially developed system of general-developing exercises.

The following differential tasks were taken from the special education system for primary school students and selected according to age. For example, depending on the division of boys and girls, the following tasks are given.

Task 1. Leaning: boys - 1.5 minutes, girls - 1 minute.

Task 2. Finding a new way to complete a certain combination based on the elements learned: for boys and girls.

Depending on the areas of interest of the students, the following differential assignments are given. The percentage is the same for all elementary school students, but health, physical fitness is weak, average, strong, etc. For the following reasons: Therefore, the physical education teacher divides the class into three groups and performs three types of exercises - easy, moderately difficult, complex. In the process of explaining and demonstrating the performance in words, it is better to let the students make their own choices, choosing between easy, medium difficulty and difficult.

Task 1. Games and exercises with light elements are recommended to develop hand muscles that can be performed without tools.

Task 2. Jumping or hoop exercises are recommended.

Task 3. Types of exercises performed with a gymnastic chair are recommended.

The following differential tasks were selected from the system of special general development exercises and given depending on the health level of students. The first task is the easiest. It gets more complicated in later tasks. After learning the tasks, the students will complete the selected one.

Task 1. The starting position is standing, both feet are at shoulder level. 1 - right-handed belt. 2 - the left hand is on the waist. 3 - right hand to the shoulder. 4- the left hand is on the shoulder. 5 - right hand up. 6 - left hand up. 7-8-9-10 - head claps. 11 - lower the left hand to the shoulder.

12 - lower the right hand to the shoulder. 13 - lower the left hand to the waist. 14 - lower the right hand to the waist. 15-16 - hands forward, clapping.

Task 2. Imitation exercises. Goose walking imitation. Starting position - walking, hands on the waist, back straight. 1 - forward with the right foot. 2- forward with the left foot. 6-8 steps.

Task 3. "Clockwork". The starting position is standing, legs apart, hands on both sides 1- raise the left wrist, palm down, right wrist, palm up. 2- move the right wrist, palm down and the left wrist, palm up. 3-6 - repeat 1 and 2. The starting position is standing, legs apart, hands on both sides. 7- turn the waist to the left, raise the left wrist with the palm down, and the right wrist with the palm up. 8- turn the waist to the right, lower the right wrist with the palm down and raise the left wrist with the palm up. 9-12 - repeat 7 and 8. 13 - return to the original position.

Task 4. Bowing. Starting position - basic standing, hands on the waist. 1- bend one step forward with the left leg. 2- legs apart, hands on both sides. 3- bringing the right foot closer to the left foot. 4 - walking, putting both hands on the knees, bowing the head. 5- return to the initial state. 6 - take a step forward with the left leg, bend forward. 7- legs apart, hands on both sides. 8-

bringing the right foot closer to the left foot. 9- walking, putting both hands on the knees, bowing the head. 10- return to the initial position 11- step forward with the right leg, bend forward. 12- legs apart, hands on both sides. 13. Bringing the left leg closer to the right leg. 14- walking, putting both hands on the knees, bowing the head. 15- return to the original state. 16 - one step forward with the right leg, bending forward. 17- legs apart, hands on both sides. 18- bringing the left foot closer to the right foot. 19- walking, putting both hands on the knees, bowing the head. 20 - return to the initial state.

It is important to follow a "light to heavy" position when designing differentiation exercises. Exercises should be short; training conditions should be clear and understandable.

K.G. Selevko defines differentiated instruction as an "educational process" defined as a form of working with a class of students grouped together according to common qualities important for learning.

Another requirement from a didactic point of view in the process of forming the skills of independent performance of general development exercises in elementary school students is to pay constant attention to the direction, because the skills of planning, independent organization are formed. Self-management skills are important in the process of self-management of elementary school students.

In conclusion, it can be said that taking into account the purpose and setting of the task proposed by the teacher during the independent performance of general development exercises plays a big role in the formation of students' planning, independent organization, and self-control skills. Differentiated education, taking into account the individual needs of students, is an effective tool in developing the skills of independent performance of exercises. Through this approach, each student is provided with personalized exercises, and their abilities and potential are fully realized.

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